

Preservation and conservation of library resources in academic libraries of West Bengal: A study

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Abstract: *The current study focuses on the state of preservation and conservation efforts in West Bengali academic libraries. A total of sixty libraries have been chosen for this investigation. The outcome reveals that 98.33% of libraries regularly do cleaning and dusting tasks. Additionally, it demonstrates that 90% of libraries take action by binding their older volumes. Eighty-five percent of libraries have their own security systems. In 71.67% of the libraries, photocopiers are available. A sizable number of libraries have started their own digital libraries. Sixty percent of the libraries concurred that financing for conservation and preservation efforts is insufficient.*

Keywords: Academic library, preservation, conservation, library books, dusting and cleaning, document management

1 Introduction

Preservation and access are two complementary goals among libraries' core missions. It is pointless to preserve only for the sake of preservation, and providing unrestricted access to all materials without considering preservation strategies may eventually result in the documentary legacy becoming unreachable for future generations. The two main components of preservation are conservation and restoration. They deal with the upkeep and repairs of documentary resources on a physical level.

The study investigated the various techniques used in the preservation and conservation of library materials in selected college library in West Bengal. Particularly, it examined the total collection of library materials and number of their different physical forms, preservation and conservation polices and constraints limiting effective preservation and conservation.

Preservation and conservation work by college libraries is not a new issue to the library professionals. There are lots of works about it before done around the world. Some of them are Baker and Soroka (1978) asking "way preservation?" and gives some values of the nature of library materials; causes of deterioration; the role of the librarian; the roles of the conservator and the scientist; binding; manuscripts and documents; preservation; micro recording and other copying methods; disaster and salvage; and National planning. A Symposium on the preservation of library and archival materials in Southern Africa was held at the South African Library to promote awareness amongst information workers of the urgent need to conserve and preserve the Southern African literary heritage (Symposium on the Preservation of Library and Archival Materials in Southern Africa, 1987). In the year of 2019,

two authors concluded a study for the preservation and utilization of the former house and calligraphies, books, and other materials. But the main project was restricted to the relocation of the former house because of fund shortage. Another study was conducted on preservation and conservation in the library (Onwubiko, 1991).

Present study focuses on the preservation of library materials in present day. It has been tried to reveal the present situation of the college libraries regarding preservation and conservation of library materials.

2 Objectives

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To identify college libraries in West Bengal present conditions about their collections.
2. To find out the role of different types of college libraries to preserve those information.
3. To know the tools for preserving documents in the college libraries.
4. To find out the problems of those college libraries regarding collections.
5. Preservation and Conservation polices of those colleges.

3 Methodologies

At the beginning of the study, review of literatures has been completed by searching ProQuest, SCOPUS and websites of various universities and Sodh-Ganga, Google search, Google Scholar etc. for selecting and searching the related literatures.

Purposing sampling has been followed to conduct this present study. Data has been collected from six libraries in various districts in W.B. such as Bankura, Bardhaman, Birbhum, Coachbihar, East Midnapore, West Midanapur, Hooghly, Howrah, Kolkata, Jalpaiguri, Malda, North 24 Pgs, South 24 Pgs, Darjeeling etc. Sometimes it collected applying by interview method or by telephonic method or via WhatsApp. Moreover, seventeen college libraries have been physically visited for capturing data and to under the present situations. For collecting primary data, close ended questionnaires have been used in those cases. After that, Microsoft Excel has been used for comparison and analysis of the collected data.

4 Data Analysis

4.1 Type of colleges

It is needed because to know from where the data is collected, to know specific figure of selected Government colleges and Government aided colleges of W.B.

Table 1: Statement showing category of colleges

Sl. No	Types	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Government	5	08.33
2	Government Aided	55	91.67
Total		60	100.00

A pie chart has been given below by using the above table.

Chart.1: Category of colleges taken in this study

Results: The study includes 8.33% of government colleges and 91.67% of government aided colleges. It shows that out of 60 colleges, maximum number of colleges are affiliated by the University of Calcutta and Burdwan University, Kalyani University, North Bengal University, West Bengal State university, Vidyasagar University and Bankura University, Kazi Nazrul University in West Bengal.

4.2 Grade of Colleges

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in India are evaluated and accredited by the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), an agency of the Indian government. The following table shows the grades of the colleges under study.

Table .2: Statement showing NAAC grade colleges

Sl. No.	NAAC Grade	No. of colleges	Percentage of colleges
1	A+	2	03.34
2	A	6	10.00
3	B++	11	18.34
4	B+	9	15.00
5	B	19	31.67
6	C+	1	01.66

Sl. No.	NAAC Grade	No. of colleges	Percentage of colleges
7	C	7	11.66
8	No Grade	5	08.33
Total		60	100.00

Chart .2: Category of NAAC Grade of colleges

Results: The results indicate that the least number of grade holders is C+ (i.e. 1.66%), and the largest number of grade holders are colleges with a B grade (31.67%). Two colleges only have an A+ grade (i.e. 3.34%).

4.3 Library Collections & preservation work

Library materials are referred to as library collections. The primary goal of library collections is to preserve materials for future generations. It is needed to know the preservation frequency of library collections for their collected materials.

Table- 3: Collection wise frequency of preservation work:

Sl. No.	Collection wise number of libraries do preservation work						
		Up to 10,000	10,001-20,000	20,001-30,000	30001-40000	Above 40000	Total
1	Once in a year	0	8	5	6	13	32
2	Twice in a year	0	6	1	0	3	10
3	More than 4 times	0	4	3	4	3	14
4	Never	1	0	2	0	1	4
Total Colleges		1	18	11	10	20	60

Chart 3: Total collections and frequency of preservation work

Results: From the above chart and table, it can be concluded that the libraries having higher collections maintain their preservation work more frequently. Most of the colleges maintain their preservation related work once in a year. It is clear that the libraries with collections upto 10,000 do not maintain their preservation work regularly.

4.4 Library collection & conservation work

Conservation refers to more active techniques to maintain a book's current condition or even return it to a previous state. For a considerable amount of time, book conservation work for the library must be undertaken. Numerous libraries perform this task once, twice, or three times a year. The frequency found in this investigation is as follows.

Table 4: Statement showing frequency of conservation work:

Sl No.	Time Frame	No. of Libraries	Persentages
1	0-6 Months	16	26.67
2	1 Year	27	45.00
3	2 Years	7	11.66
4	2 Years above	4	06.66
5	When require	1	01.67
6	Never	5	08.34
Total		60	100.00

A pie chart has been given below by using the above table.

Chart 4: The pie chart showing frequency of conservation work

Results: Among the 60 colleges, maximum number (45%) of colleges in West Bengal follow conservation work once in a year i.e. 27 colleges. Only 26% of colleges do their conservation work two times in a year and 11% of colleges do their work twice in a year. 8.34% of colleges do not follow any conservation work and 1.67% of colleges do this work when needed.

4.5 Presrvation techniques

The libraries employ several methods of conservation and preservation. However, a restricted method has been discovered in college libraries. The following methods have been used in those libraries, according to the current study.

Table 5: Statement showing various presrvation techniques

Sl No.	Preservation Techniques	No.of colleges	Percentage
1	Binding	54	90.00
2	Cleaning and Dusting	59	98.33
3	Deacidification	0	0
4	Fumigation	9	15.00
5	Insect repellent	50	83.33
6	Laminataion	2	03.33
7	Photocopying	43	71.66
8	Scanning	40	66.66
9	Security System	51	85.00

A bar chart has been given below by using the above table.

Chart 5: The bar chart showing different kinds of presrvation techniques

Results: The table and figure above demonstrate that nearly all college libraries (98.33%) regularly dust and clean their spaces. Ninety percent of libraries take action by binding their older volumes. The fact that 85% of the libraries are aware of their security systems. In 83.33% of college libraries, pesticide is used as an insect deterrent. The smallest percentage of libraries (15%) employ fumigation methods. There is not a single library that employs deacidification methods.

4.6 Preservation & conservation measures

It is necessary to determine which types of measures are being utilized for preservation & conservation in the college libraries.

Table 6: Different measures taken by the libraries

Sl. No.	Measures	No. of colleges	Percentages on total colleges
1	Air conditioners (AC)	20	33.33
2	Computer	59	98.33
3	Fumigation chamber	7	11.66
4	Lamination machine	2	3.33
5	Photocopy machine	43	71.66
6	Scanner	40	66.66
7	Security instruments	51	85

A bar chart has been given below by using the above table.

Chart 6: Bar chart showing different techniques used by the libraries

Results: As can be seen from the table and chart, 98.33% of college libraries have computers for preservation. Photocopy machines (71.66%) and security devices (85%) are common in libraries. A sizable portion of college libraries (66.66%) have scanners available for scanning rare and antiquated materials. The lowest percentage of college libraries (3.33%) have laminating machines. It's great that air conditioning is now installed in so many libraries.

4.7 Physical form of binding materials

The present study finds at least 100 different types of binding materials. Many of the colleges have both cloth and leather binding books and others have only cloth binding books. Palm leaf binding materials are found in the fewest libraries. The study finds the true pictures of binding materials as follows.

Table 7: Different physical form of binding materials

Sl. No.	Binding materials	No. of colleges	Percentages on total colleges
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1	Cloths	18	30
2	Leather	21	35
3	Paper	60	100
4	Palm Leaf	3	5

A bar chart has been given below by using the above table.

Chart .7: Different physical form of binding materials

Results: According to the above chart and the bar talk, documents in cloth binding are found in 18 libraries (30%), whereas documents in leather binding are found in 21 libraries (35%). Every one of the sixty libraries has volumes bound in paperback. Three libraries (5%) have the fewest number of palm leaf books with palm leaf cover binding.

4.8 Digital Library Initiation

Nowadays, a large number of libraries have started to construct digital library systems on their own. The current study provides an update on the situation.

Table 8: Statements showing digital library system

Sl. No.	Digital Library	No. of Colleges	Percentages
1	Initiation fully	11	18.34
2	Initiation-in-progress	16	26.66
3	No Initiation	33	55.00
Total		60	100

Chart 8: Status of digital library initiation phase

Results: Only 11 libraries (18.34%) have successfully started digital libraries at their institutions, according to the above table and chart, and 16 libraries (26.66%) have stated that their work on starting digital libraries is still in process. Rest of the libraries i.e. 33 libraries (55%) do not take any initiative regarding digital library system.

4.9 Barrier of preservation and conservation work

The college libraries in West Bengal face numerous obstacles when it comes to conservation and preservation efforts. Numerous obstacles are found in the current investigation. A synoptic perspective of this can be seen in the table below.

Table 9: Barrier of preservation and conservation works

Sl. No.	Types of Barriers	No. of Colleges	Percentage on total colleges
1	Inadequate Funding	36	60
2	Infrastructure	15	25
3	Lack of Man Power	45	75
4	Others	15	25

Using the table above, a bar chart is shown below.

Chart 9: Barrier of preservation and conservation work

Results: According to the table and chart, 36 institutions (60% of them) struggle with insufficient finance and infrastructural challenges are faced by 15 colleges (25%) in order to complete preservation and conservation-related tasks. Forty-five institutions (75%) specifically mention that their libraries are understaffed, while the remaining colleges (25%) list a variety of issues, including administrative and other issues.

5. Recommendations

The study discovered that there are numerous drawbacks to conservation and preservation in college libraries. Regarding the conservation and preservation of library holdings, a number of proposals have been made to improve college libraries.

1. There should be regular trainings through workshops and seminars on preservation and conservation.
2. Since the preservation and protection of these library items are essential, it is important to learn how to handle, store, and preserve them.
3. The library needs infrastructure and other items to support its preservation efforts in addition to human resources to grow and thrive.
4. Sufficient funding is necessary for the library to operate well; in particular, sufficient funding is required to obtain the best results in this area relative to the other elements.
5. If structural changes are needed, they should try to comply with green library standards.
6. Insufficient preservation and conservation tools in college libraries directly impact on the collection development in libraries. Therefore, these devices need to be purchased right away, when needed.
7. It is necessary to make sure that a wide bandwidth IT infrastructure is available to support conservation and preservation efforts.

6. Conclusion

Library materials are the heart of libraries. They are essential to education, information providers, the preservation of knowledge for the future, and the ability to understand the past. All college libraries, whatever of size, ought to have a clear plan in place for safeguarding the resources they hold. Staff

members and users should understand their responsibilities within the preservation program when making plans for preservation. The lifespan of books or other materials significantly diminished over time if they were not maintained adequately. Thus, frequent preservation and conservation work is crucial in those libraries. In addition to aiming to obtain materials, college libraries should make sure that such items are maintained and preserved so that future generations of students can use them. As the saying goes, "prevention is better than cure," deterioration of library items can be minimized or avoided even though damage to them is occasionally unavoidable.

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